

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Advertising media and consumer behaviour: A case study of Coca-Cola and Pepsi media influence on brand promotion and consumer choice

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to examine the role advertising media plays in promoting products, how the advertising strategies employed by companies resonate with their target audience/consumers, and how they influence consumer buying behaviour. Building on previous studies that focus on advertising, this research took a step further by examining the specific media through which advertisements are delivered. The results revealed that Coca-Cola and Pepsi consumers preferred advertisements executed through television. The findings also indicated that consumers are drawn to the products due to the advertising media used by the companies. Furthermore, the study supports the AIDA model's proposition regarding the steps involved in leading an individual to make a purchase decision.

Keywords: Advertising media; Consumer Behaviour; Product

1. Introduction

Advertisement, one of the promotional tools used in marketing a product or service, is a key strategy employed by organisations and companies to reach their target audience. It is designed to appeal to consumers' decision-making processes, encouraging them to purchase products or request services. Saulawa, Tanko, and Saulawa (2024), citing Kotler (2014), assert that *advertisement is a promotional tool in transforming and improving the sale of consumer goods, through which customers become aware of the quality, functionality, quantity, and price of a consumer product, as well as the address of the company or manufacturing sector that produces it.* Similarly, Pelsmacker, Geuens, and Bergh (2001), as cited in Onasanya (2014), explain that advertising is generally known as mass media content intended to persuade readers, viewers, or listeners to take action regarding products, services, or ideas. It also serves to create a mental image in the minds of the public, from which consumers may be drawn—especially if an effective advertising message is used and delivered through appropriate channels.

Furthermore, Moeneke, as cited by Okoroigbo (2005), describes advertising as *"messages published in newspapers, billboards, radio, television, and cinema for products and services."* For advertising to be meaningful and achieve its intended purpose, it must employ media as a conduit to deliver its messages to a target audience. The media serve as channels through which advertising messages are disseminated to a broad, heterogeneous audience, taking into account factors such as demographic status, location, experience, exposure, and educational background. According to Dermawan and Barkar (2022), advertising is *"a communication used to convey messages to many people. The importance of effective communication in delivering the message is crucial to achieving the advertisement's objectives. The effectiveness of any advertisement lies in its message; the message itself persuades both existing and prospective consumers by appealing to their purchasing instincts, thereby distinguishing one product from another."*

It is essential to consider the channels through which advertising messages are delivered to the target audience, as consumers do not all have access to the same media. Some may have access to television, others to radio, the internet,

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newspapers, or magazines. For example, some products gain more patronage when advertised through television due to its wide audience reach, while others perform better on social media, thanks to recent technological advancements across the globe. Sunanda (2010) also affirms that *in short, we may say that the success of advertising depends upon the right selection of media, the timely release of the advertisement message, its frequency and continuity, and the place of its release*. Advertising media can generally be divided into two categories: above-the-line and below-the-line media (Dermawan & Barkar, 2022).

Previous studies on the importance of advertising have established that it helps create awareness about a product or service, retain existing consumers, and attract potential ones. For instance, studies conducted by Adekoya (2011) and Naveen (2013) revealed that advertising is used to promote products in ways that attract significant patronage. Similarly, Onifade (2011) concluded in his findings that advertising messages help advertisers achieve their goals by influencing consumer behaviour through persuasive messaging. In addition, a study by Dermawan and Barkar (2022) examined the importance of effective communication in advertising messages and how it contributes to the delivery of advertisements. The results showed that advertising does not always succeed in clearly conveying its intended message. Therefore, effective communication is necessary to ensure that advertisements are clear, understandable, aligned with the offer being made, and capable of capturing consumer interest.

Furthermore, Suku, Pramod, and Matthew (2023) explored the effectiveness of advertising through television and YouTube by analysing various aspects of advertisements on both platforms. Their study revealed that YouTube advertisements have a more immediate impact on recipients compared to television adverts. It also demonstrated that YouTube allows businesses to use more precise targeting options than television. Based on the foregoing discussion on advertising, this study focuses on advertising media and investigates how it aids in promoting products and services, the effectiveness of selecting the appropriate media for advertisements, and the influence of advertising media on consumer behaviour.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1. Advertising Media

Arens, Weigold, and Arens (2008) assert that *the media that carries the advertiser's message is a vital connection between the company that manufactures a product or offers a service and the customer who may wish to buy it*. Examples of advertising media (Osisanwo, 2013) include cinema houses, television, radio, billboards, the internet, posters, handbills, catalogues, magazines, newspapers, free samples, mechanical devices, window dressing, labels, wrapper papers, tickets, signs, show cards, footballers' shirts, T-shirts, table mats, tins, bottles, calendars, diaries, buses, cars, containers, cups, plates, notebooks, chairs, tables, and other items. These examples can be categorised into broadcast, online, outdoor, print, product placement, and print advertising (Qader, Hamza, Anwer, and Anwer, 2022).

2.2. Consumer Purchasing Behaviour

Consumer behaviour is based on the concept that an individual may decide to purchase a product or service on the spot (Adelaar, Chang, Lanchndorfer, Lee, & Morimoto, 2003). Abideen and Salsam (2005) explain this by stating that *consumer behaviour is predicted from consumer attitude when consumers buy the brand which they like most*. An audience is unlikely to decide to purchase a product if the advertisement is ineffective or if the wrong advertising medium is selected to deliver the message. Goldsmith and Lofferty (2002) affirm this by stating that *effective advertisement influences the attitude towards the brand and finally leads to purchase intention*. Similarly, Ashcroft and Hoey (2001) state that *action is the behaviour stage involving actual purchasing*, while Hoyer and Macinnis (2009) as cited by Meshesha (2018) that *effective advertising creates positive feelings that lead to actual purchase of the advertised product*. According to Hassan (2015) citing Guolla (2011) describes consumer behaviour as *the process and activity by which people select, purchase, evaluate, and consume the product or service to satisfy a need or want*, while Ali (2005) defines advertising as a marketing concept that aims to influence the buying behaviour of customers. Adekoya (2011) also found that *advertising influences consumer buying behaviour, which means that it helps to increase sales turnover*.

2.3. Advertising and Consumers' Buying Behaviour

The primary objective of advertising is to reach prospective consumers in order to influence their awareness, attitudes, and buying behaviour (Abideen & Salman, 2005). Effective advertising influences consumers' attitudes toward a brand, which subsequently leads to purchase intention (Goldsmith & Lafferty, 2002). According to Samar and Lodhi (2015), "advertisements have been used for many years to influence the buying behavior of consumers." Advertising plays a significant role in shaping consumers' buying behaviour by creating awareness of a product or service, shaping perceptions, and generating interest and desire (Gani, 2024). Similarly, Soti (2024) asserts that advertising can

influence consumers' purchase intentions by highlighting the unique benefits and value proposition of a product or service. Khan (2006) defines consumer behaviour as “the decision-making process and physical activity involved in acquiring, evaluating, using, and disposing of goods and services.”

Furthermore, advertising media serve as a means to convey persuasive and appealing messages intended to influence consumer purchasing decisions. At the initial stage, a consumer may have no intention to make a purchase; however, exposure to an advertisement—whether seen, heard, or read—can lead to a change in behaviour that results in a purchase decision. Advertisers achieve this by strategically crafting messages that resonate with the characteristics and needs of their target audience. For example, Paracetamol, a pain relief medication, often features imagery of a man suffering from a headache due to hard labour, thereby suggesting that individuals experiencing similar symptoms should use the product to restore their health.

2.4. Empirical Studies

Numerous studies have been conducted on the role, effect, influence, and significance of advertising, and the findings have contributed valuable suggestions and recommendations. These studies have examined advertising as a means of promoting a product, exposing it to the public, changing consumers' perceptions, and influencing their buying behaviour. This study aims to contribute to the existing body of literature by focusing on the role of advertising media. A study by Zhao, Butt, Murad, Mirza, and Al-Faryan (2022), titled *Untying the Influence of Advertisements on Consumers' Buying Behaviour and Brand Loyalty Through Brand Awareness: The Moderating Role of Perceived Quality*, examined how advertising affects consumer buying behaviour and brand loyalty, with brand awareness serving as a mediator and perceived quality as a moderating variable. The study, which focused on the growing cosmetics industry, found that advertisements significantly predicted brand awareness, brand loyalty, and consumer buying behaviour. Similarly, Garg, Raj, Kumar, Singh, Pahuja, and Sehrawat (2023), in their study *Elucidating the Role of Consumer Decision-Making Style on Consumers' Purchase Intention: The Mediating Role of Emotional Advertising Using PLS-SEM*, explored the impact of emotional advertising on consumer decision-making styles and purchase intention. Their findings indicated that emotional advertising plays a significant strategic role in influencing consumer buying behaviour.

Sama (2019), in a study titled *The Impact of Media Advertisements on Consumer Behaviour*, investigated the impact of television, radio, newspapers, magazines, and internet advertisements on the five stages of consumer behaviour—awareness, interest, conviction, purchase, and post-purchase behaviour. The results showed that newspapers were the only medium that had a significant impact across all five stages. In another study, Jemala and Melese (2025), *The Impact of Advertising on Consumers' Buying Behaviour: The Case of Safaricom Ethiopia, Addis Ababa*, examined how advertisement characteristics—such as impressiveness, simplicity, attention-grabbing elements, memorability, creativity, and honesty—affect consumer buying behaviour in relation to telecommunications products and services. The study revealed that impressive, memorable, and creative advertisements had a statistically significant positive impact on consumer buying behaviour, whereas simplicity, attention-grabbing features, and honesty did not. Furthermore, Rahmi, Tayeb, and Amerkhail (2020), in their study *The Impact of Advertising on Consumer Buying Behaviour*, conducted in Kabul Province, found that emotional responses, environmental perceptions of brands, brand awareness, and sensory-stimulated advertising all had a positive relationship with consumer buying behaviour.

2.5. Theoretical Framework

2.5.1 Aida Model

AIDA is an acronym for *Awareness, Interest, Desire, and Action*. This model is used to guide the audience from the stage of becoming aware of a product or service to the point of ultimately patronizing it (Jayson, 2013). According to Jílková and Králová (2019), citing Solomon (2010) asserts that the key to successfully implementing the AIDA model is understanding the buyer's mental state. This is a highly complex process that requires both skill and experience.

SOURCE: Knowledge Brief (2016) <https://www.kbmanage.com/concept/aida-concept>

Figure 1 AIDA Model of Communication

Awareness

Its primary aim is to attract the audience to its product or service. McFarlin (2016) states that an advertiser "must first capture the viewers' attention, which is an essential component of any advertising campaign." This can be achieved by using messages that arouse the audience's curiosity and create a desire to learn more about the product. Jayson (2013) asserts that "the first hurdle for any piece of writing is to capture the reader's attention."

Interest

This stage is aimed at raising the customer's interest by demonstrating the product's features, advantages, and benefits (Ford, 2016). Jayson (2013) asserts that "the key here is to use informative persuasion techniques and as much proof as you can find to hold the reader's attention once you have captured it."

Desire

This is the stage where the advertiser aims to show prospects how the product or service can solve their problems by highlighting its features and demonstrating how the benefits will meet their needs (Chris, 2016). Ford (2016) simply puts it as "convince customers that they want and desire the product or service and that it will satisfy their needs."

Action

This is the stage where those whose attention has been drawn to the product or service are encouraged to develop an interest, which then leads to a desire to take the action of patronage. This stage helps determine whether the advertisement has achieved its purpose—attracting customer patronage. Ford (2016) describes it as aiming to "lead customers towards taking a specific and measurable action."

As represented in Figure 1, an advertisement follows a series of stages that an advertiser must guide a prospective consumer through before a purchase can occur. Advertisements do not typically elicit an immediate behavioral response; instead, they must follow these stages to prompt or motivate people to buy the product. From the diagram, it can be observed that the model begins with a large number of people at the first stage, but this number decreases progressively as each stage is approached.

3. Methodology

The study adopted a survey research method to obtain data from the study population, which included youths and adults between the ages of 16 and 60 who purchase or consume Coca-Cola and Pepsi. The sampling techniques used were purposive and convenience sampling, and the instrument employed was a questionnaire. A total of two hundred and fifty (250) questionnaires were administered, with one hundred and twenty-five (125) respondents for each drink. Frequency tables and percentages were used to analyze the data collected, and the findings were presented in tabular form. Based on this exercise, findings related to the research questions were discussed, and a summary is provided below. People between the ages of 26 and 35 consume these drinks more than other age groups, such as 16–25, 36–49, and 50–60. Among the two hundred and fifty participants, males represented the highest number of consumers of Coca-Cola and Pepsi compared to females, and many of these consumers were single.

4. Data Analysis

This section presents an analysis and discussion of the findings of the data gathered for the study. The interpretation of findings is done through the use of tables of frequency count and percentage.

Table 1 The cause of attraction to the product's advertisements

Variable	Frequency <i>Pepsi</i>	Percentage <i>Pepsi</i>	Frequency <i>Coca-Cola</i>	Percentage <i>Coca-Cola</i>
Colour	17	13.6%	14	11.2%
Picture	40	32%	41	32.8%
Text	4	3.2%	12	9.8%
Advertising Media	64	51.2%	12	9.6%
Total	125	100%	125	100%

Table 1 shows the factor that attracts respondents to advertisements. The result shows that advertising media is the major factor that attracts respondents to product advertisements.

Table 2 Respondents' responses according to the advertising media they have access to

Variable	Frequency <i>Pepsi</i>	Percentage <i>Pepsi</i>	Frequency <i>Coca-Cola</i>	Percentage <i>Coca-Cola</i>
Television	60	48%	68	48%
Radio	21	16.8%	18	14.4%
Billboard	16	12.8%	16	12.8%
Handbill	6	4.8%	2	1.6%
Newspaper	8	6.4%	8	6.4%
Magazine	2	1.6%	-	-
Internet	12	9.6%	13.4	10.4%
Total	125	100%	125	100%

Table 2 shows the results regarding the media through which respondents access advertisements. It reveals that a larger percentage of respondents access advertisements through television compared to other media. The next two most frequently selected media are radio and the internet.

Table 3 The Extent To Which Advertising Media Influence Consumers' Buying Behaviour

Variable	Frequency <i>Pepsi</i>	Percentage <i>Pepsi</i>	Frequency <i>Coca-Cola</i>	Percentage <i>Coca-Cola</i>
Yes	74	59.2%	69	55.2%
No	51	40.8%	56	44.8%
Total	125	100%	125	100%

Table 3 presents the analysis of the extent to which advertising media influence consumer behaviour. The results show that the advertising media used by the products considered have a significant effect on consumers' buying behaviour. This implies that there is a greater likelihood of consumers taking action if they are reached through a medium they have access to. These findings align with the assertion of Dompey and Baidoo (2024) that "media advertising plays an influencing role in the different stages of consumer buying behaviour – from awareness, interest, and conviction to purchase and post-purchase." They also support the results of the study by Ramya and Suraj (2024), which state that "there is a significant and complex influence of advertising media on the purchasing behaviour of consumers. Businesses can effectively influence consumer purchasing decisions by knowing their target audience, choosing the right channels, keeping messaging consistent, utilising data for optimisation, producing engaging and personalised content, collaborating with influencers, optimising for mobile platforms, and prioritising ethical considerations.

Table 4 Advertising media preferred by consumers

Variable	Frequency <i>Pepsi</i>	Percentage <i>Pepsi</i>	Frequency <i>Coca-Cola</i>	Percentage <i>Coca-Cola</i>
Television	75	60%	75	60%
Radio	14	11.2	11	8.8%
Billboard	19	15.2%	22	17.6%
Handbill	-	-	4	3.2%
Newspaper	3	2.4%	4	3.2%
Magazine	1	0.8%	-	-
Poster	-	-	1	0.8%
Internet	13	10.4%	8	6.4%
Total	125	100%	125	100%

Table 4.4 reveals the most preferred advertising medium among the respondents. The results show that television is the most favoured medium across different age groups. Several reasons are attributed to respondents' preference for television advertisements, which aligns with the findings of several authors. Ayanwale, Alimi, and Ayanbimipe (2005) found in their study that 71.43% of respondents selected television as their most preferred medium. Ebrahimian and Ansari (2011) affirm that "TV advertising was effective in capturing customers' attention, creating interest, desire, and prompting the action of purchasing." Similarly, Sama (2019) states that TV advertising has a significant impact on the awareness, interest, and conviction stages of consumer behaviour. In Osman (2020), the study revealed that television is the advertising medium consumers find most attractive, with 42% of respondents selecting it as their preferred medium.

5. Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study show that consumer behaviour is greatly influenced by product advertisements and the advertising media used to convey promotional messages to both existing and prospective consumers. The result resonates with the position of Ansari and Arash (2016) that "advertising media selection has the strongest relationship with brand advertising success and effectiveness and can be considered as the most important factor affecting advertising effectiveness". Consequently, it can be established that advertising media play a significant role in consumers' purchasing decisions. This implies that if the appropriate advertising media are employed to reach different consumer segments, patronage of such products will be greatly increased. The findings also reveal that advertising media create awareness through various channels such as television and radio, among others. This aligns with the

findings of Ahsan and Shadd (2015), who revealed that advertising helps to promote a product by exposing consumers to its advertisement. This is further supported by the results of Kumar and Raju (2013), which show that advertising helps to convince consumers to buy a product and is regarded as a powerful communication medium that conveys the intentions of the producer or advertiser to both existing and prospective consumers. Based on these findings, it is evident that advertising effectiveness depends largely on the medium used to convey the message.

The findings of this study concerning the importance of advertising media in promoting products through advertising are consistent with the AIDA model. The model demonstrates that advertisements guide consumers through different stages before a purchase is made. These stages indicate that advertising, when delivered through the appropriate media, makes consumers aware of a product and ultimately leads them to take action by purchasing it.

6. Conclusion

One of the key instruments required to promote a product is advertising. Therefore, it must be effectively utilised to achieve this purpose. The findings highlight the role played by advertising media in reaching the target audience, who may be either existing or prospective consumers. It can be concluded from the findings that each consumer has access to at least one form of advertising media, including television, radio, billboards, handbills, newspapers, magazines, and the internet. The results indicate that the type of advertising media used to convey messages to the target audience can either enhance or undermine the effectiveness of an advertisement, and it significantly influences consumer buying behaviour. This implies that product manufacturers or advertisers must acknowledge the importance of advertising media and select the medium most accessible to their target consumers. The study clearly shows that more people have access to television than to other media. Therefore, advertisers and manufacturers should ensure that particular attention is given to television advertising. Nonetheless, other media also have their advantages in reaching segments of the audience who have access to them.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that product manufacturers and advertisers take into cognisance the advertising media that will effectively convey their messages to the target audience—both existing and prospective consumers. They should also recognise that consumers have access to different forms of advertising media. Some have access only to television, others to radio, and some to the internet, among other platforms. Television advertisements should be given particular attention, as the results show that a larger percentage of respondents have access to and prefer television over other advertising media, finding it more engaging. Furthermore, manufacturers and advertisers should utilise all available advertising media to appeal to a broader consumer base. Repetition of advertisements across different platforms can help create a lasting impression or desire in the minds of consumers, encouraging repeat purchases and attracting prospective buyers

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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